

MODEL UPDATING OF A COMPOSITE RAILWAY BRIDGE

Case study of the Bryngeå Bridge using error domain model falsification

Marcel Hofstetter^{*,a}, John Leander^a

^aKTH Royal Institute of Technology, Dept. of Civil and Architectural Engineering, Division of Structural Engineering and Bridges, Sweden
marcelho@ug.kth.se, john.leander@byv.kth.se

ABSTRACT

When designing railway bridges, it is of utmost importance to consider the dynamic effects caused by moving train loads. In order to do so, finite element models are constructed and subjected to moving load models presented in the Eurocodes. Oftentimes, the Eurocodes provide parameter values of adequate precision for practical purposes, however for research purposes, more accurate values are sought. In order to obtain these material parameter values; an error domain model falsification (EDMF) procedure is used to perform a model updating of an FE model of the single span steel-concrete composite railway bridge named the Bryngeå Bridge on Botniabanan in northern Sweden. The parameters with uncertain values to be updated were obtained using a sensitivity analysis and determined to be the following: modulus of elasticity of the concrete deck (E_c), density of the concrete (ρ_c), density of the ballast (ρ_b), longitudinal stiffness contribution of the continuity of the rails past the bridge span (k_{rail}), and support viscous damping from the post installed viscous dampers at the movable supports ($c_{support}$). The model updating using EDMF is applied to a simplified 2D model of the bridge, comparing the calculated results with measured data for accelerations, strains in the steel girders, and beam end rotations at the movable support of the bridge. The results indicate that accurate parameter values are found for the Bryngeå Bridge, and that falsification is an efficient approach to perform model calibration. Resulting distributions imply that the parameter k_{rail} can be discarded as a material parameter for the analysis of the Bryngeå Bridge.

Keywords: Model Updating, High Speed Railways, Error Domain Model Falsification (EDMF), Steel-Concrete Composite Structures

1 INTRODUCTION

In order to achieve new design concepts for railway bridges, it is important that models are of good quality allowing reliable predictions. Regarding bridge structures, this means that accurate material parameters, corresponding well to reality, are used. Values taken from standards, such as the Eurocodes [1], provide conservative values, preferred in practical design. In the context of research, more accurate values are sought in order to explain structural behaviour. To obtain accurate material parameters, the standard approach is to perform so called model updating. Normally, a procedure called the finite element model updating method is done, where the residual between measured results and calculated results is minimized, to obtain one given set of parameters [2]. This poses a problem however, as both measurements and calculation models are afflicted with uncertainties. In this paper, another approach called EDMF is performed on the Bryngeå Bridge in Sweden in order to obtain all plausible combinations of material parameters which carry confidence based on statistical evaluation, taking into account both measurement and modelling uncertainties.

2 ERROR DOMAIN MODEL FALSIFICATION

In the context of scientific research, falsification, as formalized by Karl Popper [3], is a principle stating that models can never be fully validated by observations, they can only be falsified. In EDMF, proposed by Goulet and Smith [4], falsification is used as a tool to aid in model-based system identification. In EDMF, a *model class* $g(\dots)$ is assumed, which takes a set of n_p physical parameters as arguments ($\boldsymbol{\theta} = [\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n_p}]$). From this, a set of i predictions, $i \in (1, \dots, n_m)$ are computed, where each model instance $g_i(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is the simulated result for model class $g(\dots)$. The physical parameters can be geometry, material properties, and boundary conditions. When the true values of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ are used, depicted $\boldsymbol{\theta}^*$, along with the true modelling error, $\varepsilon_{\text{model},i}^*$, the response equals the true response, Q_i , of the system. Analogous to this, the observed results y_i along with the true measurement error $\varepsilon_{\text{measure},i}^*$, also equals Q_i . This is summarized in Eq. (1).

$$g_i(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*) - \varepsilon_{\text{model},i}^* = Q_i = y_i - \varepsilon_{\text{measure},i}^* \quad (1)$$

Models and measurements are afflicted with errors, both aleatory (such as noise and inherent natural variations in measurements) and epistemic (such as information loss due to model simplifications) [5], and a consequence from this is that the true response, along with the errors, are seldom known. Only a probability density function (PDF) can be estimated, based on information from manufacturers of monitoring equipment, and on engineering judgement. The model error $\varepsilon_{\text{model},i}$ is a realization of the model uncertainty $U_{\text{model},i}$, and the measurement error $\varepsilon_{\text{measure},i}$ is a realization of the measurement uncertainty $U_{\text{measure},i}$. A combined uncertainty, denoted $U_{c,i}$, with PDF $f_{U_{c,i}}(\varepsilon_{c,i})$, is obtained by subtracting $U_{\text{model},i}$ and $U_{\text{measure},i}$. A set of parameters is falsified if the residual between calculated and measured values fall outside the interval defined by threshold bounds $[T_{\text{low},i}, T_{\text{high},i}]$, where the bounds are obtained using Eq. (2).

$$\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n_m\}, \left\{ T_{\text{low},i}, T_{\text{high},i}: \phi^{1/n_m} = \int_{T_{\text{low},i}}^{T_{\text{high},i}} f_{U_{c,i}}(\varepsilon_{c,i}) d\varepsilon_{c,i} \right\} \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2), the parameter ϕ represents the target reliability, which is usually set to 95 % ($\phi = 0.95$) in civil engineering applications [6]. The exponent is the Šidák correction for multidimensional hypothesis testing [7]. To obtain the threshold bounds in Eq. (2), the inverse cumulative distribution function of $F_{U_{c,i}}^{-1}(x)$, $x \in [0,1]$ is used, as depicted in Eq. (3) and Eq. (4).

$$T_{\text{low},i} = F_{U_{c,i}}^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{2} (1 - \phi^{1/n_m}) \right) \quad (3)$$

$$T_{\text{high},i} = F_{U_{c,i}}^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} (1 - \phi^{1/n_m}) \right) \quad (4)$$

Based on the threshold bounds obtained from Eq. (3) and Eq. (4), the criteria for falsification is shown in Eq. (5). Model instances that does not fulfil this criteria are falsified, whereas models that do fulfil the criteria are considered candidate models, belonging to the *candidate model set*.

$$\forall i \in [1, \dots, n_m]: T_{\text{low},i} \leq g_i(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - y_i \leq T_{\text{high},i} \quad (5)$$

All models in the candidate model set are assigned an equal probability of describing the system behaviour, whereas all models that are falsified are assigned a null probability. If an entire model class $g(\dots)$ is falsified, a new model class $h(\dots)$ is assumed, taking new physical parameters as input.

3 BRYNGEÅ BRIDGE

The Bryngeå Bridge is a train bridge located close to Örnsköldsvik, on the Botniabanan in northern Sweden. The bridge consists of a single span, simply supported steel concrete composite cross-section with a single, ballasted track. The span length of the bridge is 48 m. The bridge and its cross-section are shown in *Fig. 1*. In June 2021, the bridge was retrofitted with viscous dampers at the movable supports, with the primary intention to reduce vibrations from the first bending mode of the bridge, as a part of the In2Track3 EU project [8]. Measurements indicate that the viscous dampers mitigate

the accelerations in the bridge caused by passing trains. The bridge has a long term monitoring system installed, where one of the primary intentions is to measure bridge vibrations for different trains at different train speeds. The measurement setup for the long-term monitoring system is displayed in Fig. 2. Sensors D1 and D2 are LVDT sensors placed at the upper and lower flange of the steel beam at the movable support of the southern beam, measuring horizontal displacements at the support. Uniaxial strain gauges s1 and s2 measure longitudinal strains on the upper and lower flanges respectively. Bridge-Weigh-In-Motion (BWIM) sensors BW1 and BW2 are installed to measure transverse bending at the soffit of the concrete deck in order to determine train type and speed, where train speed is found by cross correlating the signals from the BWIM sensors.

Fig. 1. The Bryngeå Bridge (a) and the cross-section of the bridge (b)

Accelerometers A1 to A4 are installed on the lower flanges of the steel beams to measure vertical accelerations. F1 to F4 are strain gauges installed on the dampers. A temperature sensor, T, was installed below the bridge deck. By measuring accelerations, the natural frequency of the first bending mode of the bridge has been determined to be $f_1 = 2.48$ Hz for positive temperatures. The traffic on the bridge is mixed, with the main train type being the Coradia X62 passenger train shown in Fig. 3. In the In2Track3 report, the critical train speed for X62 passenger trains on the Bryngeå Bridge has been calculated to be 150 km/h, which is in the operational train speed range on the bridge. Measurements also indicate that peak acceleration occurs for trains passing at about 150 km/h.

Fig. 2. Measurement setup for the long term monitoring system on the Bryngeå Bridge

Fig. 3. Coradia X62 train

4 METHOD

To perform the EDMF for the Bryngeå Bridge, several steps were performed. First, a calculation model was constructed and quality assured, as described in 4.1. Past the quality assurance, a sensitivity analysis was conducted, in order to find relevant parameters to study in the EDMF. The procedure for the sensitivity analysis is presented in 4.2. A Monte Carlo simulation was done after the sensitivity analysis to obtain calculation data, as presented in 4.3. Measurement data was then processed in order to obtain bounds for testing the models from 4.3. The procedure how the measurement data was treated is described in 4.4. Lastly, models were tested for falsification in 4.5.

4.1 Model Description and Quality Assurance

Two finite element (FE) models were constructed using ABAQUS, one 2D model and one 3D model, in order to assure the quality of the 2D FE model. Along with these, an analytical model was developed in order to further facilitate quality assurance of the FE-models. In a first step of the quality assurance, eigenfrequencies for the first three bending modes were calculated for the analytical model, in accordance with [9], and the FE models. Past this, a simulation of a passing X62 train using a moving constant load model was performed on the FE-models, and results between the two models were compared. In the subsequent analyses, the 2D model was used due to its much shorter computational time compared to the 3D model.

The 2D-model was constructed using shear flexible (Timoshenko) beam elements, with boundary conditions as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. 2D model of the Bryngeå bridge.

The rail was modelled as a separate Timoshenko beam, connected with springs, denoted k_{rail} , to the ground at its ends, as to simulate the longitudinal stiffness contribution due to the continuity of the rails [10]. At the movable support, a spring and a dashpot was added, k_{support} and c_{support} respectively, to account for the post installed viscous dampers. The rail and the bridge deck were rigidly tied together. Due to the fact that the web thickness of the steel girders vary over the bridge length (where the middle 16 meter section of the bridge had a web thickness of 20 mm and the two bridge sections closer to the supports had a web thickness of 24 mm), two different cross sections were used in the model. In ABAQUS, generalized cross sections were used for the bridge deck, and transverse shear stiffness properties were included to account for the shear flexible properties of the beam. The rails

were modelled using a single I-section. The supports were modelled as infinitely stiff, meaning soil-structure interaction was not considered in the model. The passing trains were modelled using a moving constant load model, where the load was linearly interpolated using tabular amplitudes in ABAQUS. The loads used were the axle loads from one of the train axles, taken as equal for all train axles, with an amplitude of 155 kN per axle [11]. The eigenfrequency calculation was done through a linear perturbation eigenfrequency extraction, and the train passage analysis was done using a modal dynamics step. Initially, 30 modes were used in the modal dynamics step, but due to the fact that the first 10 modes carried close to 100 % of the modal mass, only 10 modes were used in the subsequent analyses. The resulting eigenfrequencies for the first three bending modes for the three different models are presented in *Table 1* below. The material parameters used in the quality assurance were deterministic values taken from the Eurocodes [1] based on the information provided in drawings for the bridge.

Table 1. Eigenfrequency comparison between models

Vibration mode	Analytical model	2D FE model	3D FE model
1	2.29 Hz	2.29 Hz	2.27 Hz
2	7.94 Hz	7.94 Hz	7.56 Hz
3	15.0 Hz	15.0 Hz	15.2 Hz

The 3D-model contained torsional modes, which were not present in the 2D-model. To account for this in the comparison, the accelerations for sensors A1 and A3 were averaged in the 3D model, as well as the accelerations for sensors A2 and A4. Resulting time histories comparing accelerations at midpoint (averaged value for accelerometers A2 and A4) are shown in *Fig. 5*. The same averaging was subsequently done for the measurements.

Fig. 5. Midpoint acceleration comparison between 2D and 3D models

4.2 Sensitivity Analysis

To limit the amount of parameters that were checked in the analysis, a sensitivity analysis was performed to obtain the most influential parameters on the accelerations, strains and beam end rotations. To obtain probable parameter ranges for the sensitivity analysis, the JCSS probabilistic model codes [12] were used. Below in *Table 2*, the mean value, coefficient of variation (CoV), distribution type, and sources for each parameter used in the sensitivity analysis are displayed. To calculate the lower and upper bound values for parameters values taken from the probabilistic model codes – the mean value \pm two standard deviations were selected for parameters carrying a lognormal distribution. For the ballast stiffness, upper and lower bounds were dependent on the values found in the literature. In [10], the value for rail spring stiffness is given per sleeper. Based on a sleeper centre distance of 0.65 m and a stiffness of 4.72 MN/m/sleeper, the upper bound was calculated. In the sensitivity analysis, all but one parameter value was held constant, and the parameter of interest was varied between its lower bound value and its upper bound value. Based on the largest spread of results, the parameters with the largest impact were selected to be used in the EDMF Monte Carlo simulation described below.

4.3 Monte Carlo Simulation

After the sensitivity analysis, a Monte Carlo simulation was performed for the selected parameters and the determined parameter value ranges, which are written in bold in *Table 2*. In order to guarantee uniqueness of each simulation, Matlab's built in Latin Hypercube Sampling was used to determine parameter values for each simulation. It was assumed that the a priori parameter ranges were continuous uniform distributions. In total, 100,000 simulations were performed, with a total computational time of about 17 days. After the simulation, results were post-processed. The simulation was performed using Matlab in combination with ABAQUS.

Table 2. Parameters used in the sensitivity analysis. The most influential parameters are written in **bold**.

Parameter	Variable & unit	Mean	CoV	Distribution	Source
Concrete density	ρ_c (kg/m³)	2400	0.04	Lognormal	[12]
Steel density	ρ_s (kg/m ³)	7700	0.01	Lognormal	[12]
Ballast density	ρ_b (kg/m³)	2300	0.04	Lognormal	[12]
Concrete stiffness	E_c (GPa)	30.9	0.04	Lognormal	[12]
Ballast stiffness	E_b (GPa)	0.225	-	Rectangular	[14-17]
Structural damping	ξ (%)	1.9	-	Empirical	[8]
Rail spring stiffness	k_{rail} (MN/m)	88	-	Rectangular	[10]
Viscous damper stiffness	$k_{support}$ (MN/m)	0.5	-	Rectangular	[8]
Viscous damper damping	$c_{support}$ (MNs/m)	2	-	Rectangular	[8]

Based on the results in the sensitivity analysis, the number of physical parameters used were set to $n_p = 5$, being $\theta = [\rho_c, \rho_b, E_c, k_{rail}, c_{support}]$. The number of measurement points were set to $n_m = 4$. For each model instance, time histories for the accelerations at sensors A1 and A3, accelerations at A2 and A4, strains, and beam end rotations were calculated. For the accelerations, a band pass filter with cutoff frequencies of 0.5 Hz and 30 Hz was applied. The beam end rotations were calculated according to Eq. (6):

$$\alpha(t) = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{d_{LVDT1}(t) - d_{LVDT2}(t)}{dz_{LVDT}} \right) \quad (6)$$

where $\alpha(t)$ are beam end rotations, $d_{LVDT1}(t)$ and $d_{LVDT2}(t)$ are horizontal displacements at sensors D1 and D2, and dz_{LVDT} is the distance along the z-axis between the sensors, in this case $dz_{LVDT} = 2380$ mm. From the time histories, the calculated data to be used in the EDMF were as shown in Eq. (7):

$$\begin{cases} g_1(\theta) = a_{1,3,max,model} \\ g_2(\theta) = a_{2,4,max,model} \\ g_3(\theta) = \varepsilon_{s1,max,model} \\ g_4(\theta) = \alpha_{max,model} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

In Eq. (7), $a_{1,3,max,model}$ and $a_{2,4,max,model}$ are maximum absolute values of the calculated acceleration time histories, $\varepsilon_{s1,max,model}$ is the peak strain response on the lower flange of the bridge, and $\alpha_{max,model}$ is the peak value of the beam end rotation. The modelling uncertainty was assumed to be a Gaussian random variable described by $U_{model,i} \sim N(0, \sigma_{model,i})$, with standard deviation $\sigma_{model,i} = 0.05g_i(\theta)$.

4.4 Measurement Data

The long term monitoring system installed on the Bryngeå Bridge had identified 426 train passages with train speed in the interval $150 < v < 155$ km/h. This measurement series was used as a basis in the evaluation. Due to drastic changes in the bridge response for freezing temperatures, only

measurements where $T > 5$ °C were selected for the comparison, resulting in a total of 348 train passages. The accelerations for these train passages were filtered using a band pass filter, removing frequencies below 0.5 Hz and above 30 Hz. For accelerometer A1, a total of 52 signals were determined to be corrupt, these signals were removed from the sample size from both A1 and A3. The resulting sample size for accelerometers A1 and A3 were a total of 296 train passages. To account for the fact that the 2D model didn't account for torsional vibrations, measured signals from A1, A3 and A2, A4 were averaged as previously described in section 3.1. For the strains and support displacements, the signals were subtracted by the median value of the respective signals to remove effects of temperature elongation. Histograms were obtained for the peak absolute values for the accelerations, strains and beam end rotations. Normal distributions were fitted to each histogram, with expected values $\mu_{\text{calc},i}$ and standard deviations $\sigma_{\text{calc},i}$, $i \in [1, \dots, n_m]$. From the normal distributions, the measured values to be used in the EDMF were taken as $y_i = \mu_{i,\text{meas}}$. The measurement uncertainties were taken as $U_{\text{measure},i} \sim N(0, \sigma_{\text{measure},i})$.

4.5 Falsification of Models

In the final step, models were falsified or added to the candidate model set. Based on the previously calculated modelling and measurement uncertainties, a combined uncertainty was taken as $U_{c,i} \sim N(0, \sigma_{c,i})$, with standard deviation $\sigma_{c,i}$ calculated according to Eq. (8).

$$\sigma_{c,i} = \sqrt{\sigma_{\text{model},i}^2 + \sigma_{\text{measure},i}^2} \quad (8)$$

The target reliability was set to $\phi = 0.95$, threshold boundaries were calculated according to Eqs. (3) and (4), and models were tested for falsification with Eq. (5). From the resulting candidate models, input parameters for the models were extracted and plotted as normalized histograms, revealing new parameter value distributions.

5 RESULTS

5.1 Resulting Distributions for the Case Study

The normalized histograms described in 4.5 are shown in *Fig. 6* below. Numerical values for 95 % confidence intervals of the resulting parameter ranges are displayed in *Table 3*, along with the a priori intervals. A total of 2,965 model instances out of 100,000 passed the falsification test.

Table 3. Numerical values of 95 % confidence intervals for the studied parameters after EDMF, along with the a priori distribution

Parameter	A priori distribution	95 % confidence interval, posterior
E_c	[24, 45] GPa	[34.8, 44.8] GPa
ρ_c	[2200, 2600] kg/m ³	[2200, 2430] kg/m ³
ρ_b	[1560, 1840] kg/m ³	[1560, 1710] kg/m ³
k_{rail}	[0, 176] MN/m	[7.00, 173] MN/m
c_{support}	[0, 4] MNs/m	[0.03, 2.38] MNs/m

5.2 Correlation Between Studied Parameters

For the correlation between the parameters in the candidate model set, a correlation heatmap is shown in *Fig. 7*. In the figure, correlation between the physical parameters for the models in the candidate model set is shown. A value of 1 indicates perfect correlation, -1 indicates perfect anticorrelation, and 0 means no correlation. Weak correlation was observed for E_c and the two densities ρ_c and ρ_b . Weak anticorrelation was seen between ρ_c , ρ_b and c_{support} . For k_{rail} , no correlation was detected with any of the other parameters.

6 DISCUSSION

Given the fact that a candidate model set is present, the proposed model class in the article has not been falsified. All parameters but k_{rail} are heavily one-sided. Lower values of density and support viscous damping produces more candidate models, along with higher values of concrete stiffness. The resulting confidence interval of k_{rail} based on candidate models is virtually unchanged compared to the a priori distribution, meaning a candidate model can be obtained irrespective of the value of k_{rail} . The parameter k_{rail} had a large effect on the behaviour in the sensitivity analysis, however the EDMF showed that this parameter is insignificant on the bridge behaviour when studied in a probabilistic context. As for c_{support} , candidate models are mainly found for lower values – signifying that the damping effect of the viscous dampers is lower than anticipated.

Regarding correlation, very low values are obtained between all parameters. The anticorrelation between ρ_c , ρ_b and c_{support} is because these parameters govern the same behaviour, namely bridge accelerations. Bridge accelerations in the initial model (used in the quality assurance) were small in comparison to the candidate model set – which is why lower values of density and damping, along with higher values of concrete stiffness provided more candidate models.

Fig. 6. Resulting distributions from the EDMF. From left to right, up to down: Modulus of elasticity for concrete (a), concrete density (b), ballast density (c), rail longitudinal stiffness (d), support viscous damping (e)

Fig. 7. Correlation heatmap for the parameters of the candidate models.

7 CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

Based on the results and discussion presented in this paper, the main conclusions are:

1. *The distribution of k_{rail} implies that candidate models can be found without k_{rail} . In further studies, k_{rail} should be discarded from or held constant in the analysis.*
2. *The results indicate that the characteristic value of E_c suggested in the Eurocodes is significantly lower than the actual value.*
3. *The density values ρ_c and ρ_b provided in the Eurocode are higher than estimated from the model falsification.*
4. *The characteristic material values from the code do not provide the most accurate dynamic response.*

In further research, a new EDMF for the same parameters excluding k_{rail} should be performed to narrow down the distribution of the other parameters. In this paper, one model class was tested – other model classes should also be tested to explore if other parameters can produce plausible model instances. From the resulting parameter ranges in this paper, a safety index based parametric study should be performed. Lastly, convergence of parameter values should be checked to decrease the number of simulations needed.

REFERENCES

- [1] CEN, *Eurocodes Part 1990 to 1999*, European committee for standardization (CEN).
- [2] S. Avril, M. Bonnet, A.-S. Bretelle, M. Grédiac, F. Hild, P. Ienny, F. Latourte, D. Lemosse, S. Pagano, E. Pagnacco and F. Pierron, , 2008. “Overview of Identification Methods of Mechanical Parameters Based on Full-field Measurements,” *Experimental Mechanics*, vol. 48, pp. 381-402.
- [3] K. Popper, 2002. *The Logic of Scientific Discovery*, Routledge.
- [4] J.-A. Goulet and I. F. Smith, 2013. “Structural identification with systematic errors and unknown uncertainty dependencies,” *Computers and Structures*, vol. 128, pp. 251-258.
- [5] J. A. Goulet and I. F. Smith, 2013. “Predicting the Usefulness of Monitoring for Identifying the Behavior of Structures,” *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 139, no. 10, pp. 1716-1727.

- [6] I. Bayane, S. G. S. Pai, I. F. Smith and E. Brühwiler, 2021. “Model-Based Interpretation of Measurements for Fatigue Evaluation of Existing Reinforced Concrete Bridges,” *Journal of Bridge Engineering*, vol. 26, no. 8.
- [7] Z. Šidák, 1967. “Rectangular Confidence Regions for the Means of Multivariate Normal Distributions,” *Journal of the American statistical Association*, vol. 62, no. 318, pp. 626-633.
- [8] A. Andersson, R. Allahvirdizadeh, A. Seyed Hosseini Tehrani, A. Albright, P. Montenegro, G. Ferreira, M. Peixer, A. Silva, D. Ribeiro and P. Museros, 2021. “Tunnel and Bridge I2T3 Report,” Shift2Rail, Trafikverket, KTH, PORTO.
- [9] S. S. Rao, 2007. *Vibration of Continuous Systems*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- [10] J. Zakeri and K. Yousefian, 2021. “Experimental investigation into the longitudinal resistance of ballasted railway track,” in *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part F: Journal of Rail and Rapid Transit*.
- [11] U. Diehl and L. Nilsson 2017, *Svenska lok och Motorvagnar med Personvagnar*, Trafik-Nostalgiska Förlaget.
- [12] JCSS, *Probabilistic Model Code*.
- [13] E. Bourgeois, L. Soyeux and A. Le Kouby, 2011. “Experimental and numerical study of the behavior of a reinforced-earth wall subjected to a local load,” *Computers and Geotechnics*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 515-525.
- [14] G. Kumaran, D. Menon and K. Krishnan Nair, 2003. “Dynamic studies of railtrack sleepers in a track structure system,” *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, vol. 268, no. 3, pp. 485-501.
- [15] L. Ricci, V. Nguyen, K. Sab, D. Duhamel and L. Schmitt, 2005. “Dynamic behaviour of ballasted railway tracks: A discrete/continuous approach,” *Computers & Structures*, vol. 83, no. 28, pp. 2282-2292.
- [16] J. T. Shahu, K. Rao, NSV and Yudhbir, 1999. “Parametric study of resilient response of tracks with a sub-ballast layer,” *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 1137-1150.
- [17] P. Alves Costa, R. Calçada and A. Silva Cardoso, 2012. “Track-ground vibrations induced by railway traffic: In-situ measurements and validation of a 2.5D FEM-BEM model,” *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 111-128.